

INTRODUCTION

In a global economy, nations seek financial sovereignty to protect their economies from external shocks. Digital currencies can contribute to sustainability in the face of international competition.

The development of blockchain and cryptocurrency technologies provides new opportunities for creating and managing digital currencies. This allows countries to optimize their financial systems and reduce reliance on traditional currencies.

Successful integration of digital currencies can contribute to economic growth by improving access to finance and reducing transaction costs, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises. Digital currencies can improve public financial accessibility, especially in countries with low banking penetration rates.

Thus, the study and development of institutions that ensure financial sovereignty through digital currencies is relevant and essential to ensure the stability and sustainable development of all countries' economies.

The article aims to analyze the main trends in the development of institutions that ensure a country's financial sovereignty through digital currencies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials were articles from periodical peer-reviewed journals (*Quality & Quantity*, *Atlantic Economic Journal*, *Journal of Industrial and Business Economics*, *Open Economies Review*, *Journal of Banking Regulation*, *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, *Electronic Market*, *Management International Review*) and other publications focusing on financial technologies and digital currencies.

The reports of the World Bank, International Monetary Fund, and Bank for International Settlements, which analyze trends in the regulation of digital currencies and their impact on financial sovereignty, can be used as a reference.

Methods: a comparative analysis of different countries and their approaches to digital currencies and financial sovereignty to identify best practices and strategies; a case study of a specific example of a country, the Russian Federation, where the digital ruble is in a dynamic phase of development, and its introduction is expected in the future.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of digital currencies in various countries is becoming essential for the global economy. Countries worldwide are actively working on developing their digital currencies, given the growing popularity of cryptocurrencies and the need to modernize payment systems.

Q. Yao writes that the rapid development of digital technologies such as blockchain, big data, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence has significantly affected the evolution of money, giving rise to a new type of money – digital currency. In line with this trend, the digitalization of fiat currency has become the most critical monetary and financial reform in the digital age, attracting widespread attention from central banks, industries, and academia worldwide [1].

S. Singh et al. write that the emergence of cryptocurrencies and stablecoins has laid the foundation for the next wave of monetary metamorphosis. In response to private digital currencies, reserve banks are considering issuing digital versions of their fiat currencies, labeled central bank digital currencies (CBDCs). The authors conclude that the main motive is the accessibility and convenience of transfers and payments [2].

M. Lloyd points out that the introduction of digital currencies by central banks represents an essential development of money and requires public consent after extensive debate at all levels of society [3].

T. Pelagidis and E. Kostika discuss the growth of digital payments in the Eurozone, the spread of cryptocurrency trading, and the European Central Bank's intention to issue a CBDC. According to the authors, the growth of digital payments and the increased popularity of cryptocurrencies can be seen as the main driving forces behind the issuance of the digital euro [4].

A. Elson considers the problems of the dollar as the world reserve currency arising from the emergence of digital currencies. The authors discuss the prospects of replacing the dollar as the world's primary reserve currency with a composite of CBDCs [5].

P. Savona writes that central banks are considering digital sovereign currencies. However, interest in virtual products and concerns about the stability of banks and financial intermediaries slow down the decision-making process [6].

According to G. Bazzani, digital money risks becoming a techno-leviathan. However, it can also influence social dynamics by balancing competition and cooperation, reducing inequality, and creating boundaries and goals for new communities [7].

S. P. Bortnikov considers the contradictions of the independent position of the Central Bank and the Government of the Russian Federation in matters of state economic policy. It is determined that the fiat monetary system is based only on the authority of the Central Bank and the government. In contrast, cryptocurrency is based on its security system and the method of its generation: blockchain. Cashless money is seen as the premise of cryptocurrency but is controlled by a monetary center [8].

In Russia, the Central Bank is also working on a digital ruble project to make payments fast and convenient and reduce the black market [10].

China has been a pioneer in the development of CBDCs. The People's Bank of China has started testing the digital RMB (e-CNY) in several major cities. The aim is to make payments more efficient and reduce reliance on cash [9].

The Central Bank of Malaysia (Bank Negara Malaysia) is exploring the introduction of a CBDC. In 2021, the bank announced it would conduct studies and pilot projects to understand the potential benefits and risks of digital money [11].

The Central Bank of the Republic of Turkey (Türkiye Cumhuriyet Merkez Bankası) has started working on a digital currency called digital lira (e-lira). Pilot projects to test it began in 2021 to improve the payment system and increase its efficiency [12].

Bahrain has launched its CBDC and is actively testing its use in the financial sector [13; 14].

Nigeria was one of the first countries in Africa to introduce its digital currency, eNaira, officially in October 2021. It is a digital version of the Nigerian naira [15].

Digital currencies in other African countries, such as South Africa, Ghana, Kenya, Zimbabwe, Uganda, and others, are also becoming a growing topic. According to P. K. Ozili, the low interest in the Bank of Central African States's digital currency is due to the strong preference for cash payments, lack of a reliable payment system, low use of digital payments, lack of government interest in digital currency, etc. [16].

Thus, each country approaches the development of digital currency in its own way, emphasizing security, efficiency, and integration into the existing financial system.

The topic of the article is highly relevant: studying the interaction of new financial technologies and traditional financial systems and the opportunities and risks they pose to countries' economic sovereignty.

First, financial sovereignty refers to a state's ability to control its money supply and monetary system, which includes protecting the currency from foreign influence. Digital currencies, both central and private, can affect countries' financial stability and political autonomy.

The institutions that support financial sovereignty must adapt to the new environment. This includes creating regulatory frameworks that allow using digital currencies while protecting the interests of the state and its citizens.

An important aspect is also the interaction at the international level, where different countries may have different requirements and approaches to the use of digital currencies, which in turn may threaten the financial sovereignty of individual states.

Thus, the study aims to analyze the impact of digital currencies on state financial sovereignty and identify best practices and recommendations for developing institutions that ensure this sovereignty.

RESULTS

The national payment infrastructure of the Russian Federation consists of the following elements:

- the payment system of the Bank of Russia (necessary for the implementation of monetary policy and providing the possibility of interbank settlements for Russian commercial organizations);
- the Quick Payments System (provides citizens with an opportunity to make transfers by cell phone number to any banks without commission within the limit of 100,000 rubles);
- the Financial Messaging System (SPFS) (provides for the transmission of messages between banks both in Russia and abroad);
- National Payment Card System (established in 2014 based on Federal Law No. 161-FZ “On the National Payment System” dated June 27, 2011. This system serves the Mir payment system).

The national payment system began to be actively formed in 2014. Currently, the Mir system is used to make payments within the domestic retail market. It also allows making payments in some other countries, such as Belarus, Armenia, Cuba, Abkhazia, and others.

Since modern international payments are based on interbank clearing, the creation of infrastructure for the transmission of financial messages in a standardized form has become necessary within the framework of this issue. In 2014, the Bank of Russia launched the SPFS, which became an alternative to SWIFT for most Russian users. With the help of the SPFS, messages can be sent in three formats: SWIFT, ISO 20022[1], and the client's formats [17].

For Russian banks, the SPFS has become a convenient platform for transactions within the national economy under sanctions. From 2018 to 2023, the number of messages sent via the SPFS increased almost 44-fold from 5 million to 219 million units (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 Number of messages via the SPFS sent by banks domestically.
Source: compiled by the authors based on data from the Bank of Russia.

Even though the SPFS performs the same functions as SWIFT, the systems have several differences (see Table 1).

Table 1

Comparison of SPFS and SWIFT

	SWIFT	SPFS
Clients	More than 11.5 thousand banks from 200 countries	557 banks from 20 countries
Server location	USA, Europe	Russia
Reliability	“Hot” redundancy of each network element	Messages are transmitted through the Message Processing Center of the Bank of Russia.
Connection price	From 55 thousand euros	Free of charge
Service price	From EUR 10 thousand/year	Free of charge
Service tariffs	From 2.7 to 4.5 rubles per message	When sending less than 500 messages daily, an exchange participant pays 1 ruble per message; if the number of messages exceeds 500, the price is reduced to 0.8 rubles.

Message size	Up to 10 Mb	By default – 20 Kb, by separate decision – 5 Mb.
System topology	Star topology implies the presence of a system core to which many other systems are connected. The systems are not connected: each message is passed to a central link, passing information to a specific system.	Hierarchical tree topology. This topology is a subset of the “star” topology; within this topology, several hubs are used, which are hierarchically connected by star-type links.
Information storage conditions	The information storage period on the client side is unlimited; on the server – it is 124 days, and then the data are stored in the archive.	Messages are stored in the operational archive for 3 days, in the long-term archive – for 5 years.
Compliance with legislation	It cannot be used for transfers within the state as stated in Art. 16, p. 11, 161-FZ of June 27, 2011 “On the National Payment System.”	Compliant
Availability in the Russian Federation	With a limited number of banks, there is a constant risk of disconnection from the system.	Available for all banks of the Russian Federation

Source: compiled by the authors

The table above shows that the SPFS is not only an indispensable analog in the conditions of sanction restrictions, but its use is much more profitable: the Russian analog offers much lower sending and servicing tariffs than the Western system. At the same time, the SPFS is still inferior to SWIFT in terms of convenience. Thus, cross-border settlements are possible only in a few countries, while SWIFT is available globally with some exceptions. In addition, the volume of data transmitted in a SWIFT message is several times larger than that of the Russian analog.

Today, within the framework of SPFS development, the Bank of Russia sets the following tasks [18], the fulfillment of which will lead not only to greater convenience but also to an increase in the number of international users:

1. Development of the Institute of Service Bureau [3], which is necessary to increase the number of users. Now, it is possible to connect to the SPFS both directly and through a service bureau;
2. Attracting non-residents to use the SPFS. The attractiveness of the payment system for the bank is expressed, in particular, in the convenience and speed of connection. To optimize the procedure of connection and use of the SPFS, “box” solutions are being introduced (it is assumed that there is a ready-to-use product with the most necessary functions);
3. Realization of Internet access to the SPFS.

Thus, the Central Bank's main task is to attract new foreign clients to use the SPFS. Even though the SPFS is the primary channel for domestic settlements on correspondent accounts, the use of the system by foreign banks is still limited, which does not allow the Russian system to become a full-fledged alternative to SWIFT and requires significant work to attract foreign clients.

The decision of Russian businesses to continue working with frozen assets abroad and domestically based on C-type accounts through fintech and the Central Bank of Russia makes it possible, through the policy of “soft power”, to build their own models of counteraction to Donald Trump's cryptocurrency strategies, aimed at creating a new cryptocurrency and establishing U.S. leadership in the emerging quantum financial system.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The growing interest in cryptocurrencies and CBDCs gives rise to a need to explore how these instruments can affect the financial stability and sovereignty of nations.

Digital currencies can change the balance of power in the world of finance by facilitating the emergence of new centers of finance and changing the dynamics of international trade. This makes studying their impact on financial sovereignty a crucial aspect of the century of globalized financial markets.

Institutions actively developing norms and rules for digital currencies will shape new approaches to financial control and consumer protection. Academic research in this area will help identify best practices and develop more effective regulatory mechanisms.

Blockchain and related technologies are potential tools to improve the transparency and trustworthiness of financial systems [19]. Investigating their application and impact on trust in financial institutions will be essential.

New risks, such as cyber threats and fraud, come with the benefits of digital currencies. Research on security, risk management, and stability of financial systems is critical.

Questions about how digital currencies may affect financial inclusion, access to financial services, and social equity require attention and further research.

The design and implementation of strategies for digital currencies may require international cooperation [20], which opens up opportunities for interdisciplinary research in economics, law, political science, and technology.

In conclusion, the topic has significant potential for research given the current changes in financial systems and the need for new approaches to managing the sovereignty of countries in a digitized environment.

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